

Digital health skills: Practical experiences including in micro-credentialling

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On the digital health transformation front, **building partnerships** will help strengthen the available of skills and training. **Micro-credentialling**¹, in particular, is of especial importance.

On 1-2 December 2025, the Network for Digital Health Excellence (NET4DHE) held a European Digital Health Summit² at the Case de America in Madrid. The two-day platform for dialogue and collaboration concentrated on translating **policy into practice** and fostering **partnerships** among European Member States, academia, and industry.

Break-out session panellists on digital health skills (Source: European Digital Health Summit)

¹ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-01/micro-credentials%20brochure%20updated.pdf>

² <https://european-digital-health-summit.com>

Practical experiences

One of the summit's break-out sessions was on "Practical Pathways: Micro-credentials and Training Projects for Digital Health Skills". With its focus on digital health transformation, the session was geared to **skills, training, and workforce readiness**. It identified several **practical models** for capacity-building.

The session was highly pertinent, given the current stage of implementation of **Europe's Union of Skills**³, alongside everything that is also happening in relation to the European Health Data Space and especially artificial intelligence.

The session was introduced by Maddalena Illario (Reference Sites Coordination Network) and moderated by Diane Whitehouse (EHTEL). Panellists were Katja Nacevski (BRIGHTskills), Minna Isomursu (SUSA project), Jesús Pulgarin Paños (XiA project), and Lars Munter (European Health Futures Forum).

General challenges: In their debate, the four discussants tackled challenges such as:

- How partnerships can align their collaborations so as to create a **common European digital skills ecosystem**.
- How public-private partnerships can **outlive European Union-funding cycles** to deliver greater impact.
- What **governance models and incentives** can be used to prioritise digital upskilling.
- Insights into a **shared European framework on micro-credentialling**.
- The role of micro-credentialling, including e.g., **recognition and accreditation**, in fostering **workforce mobility and interoperability**.
- The **integration** of technical competences with other (transversal) skills.
- The twin importances of digital **literacy** and digital health literacy.

Among today's challenges raised for current health and care workforces were:

- Enabling personnel to spend more time with their **patients**.
- Dealing with the degree of "**churn**" (**turnover**) among personnel.
- Applying education to **real-world scenarios** and the **realities** of the healthcare market.
- Tackling other topics such as **artificial intelligence**, cybersecurity, and standards.

Practicalities: Some applied, practical, highlights included:

- Using available large-scale **platforms**.

³ https://commission.europa.eu/topics/competitiveness/union-skills_en

- Concentrating on **models, programmes, and modules** that are “intuitive to use” and are available from large-scale international organisations e.g., the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) or the World Health Organization (WHO).
- **Learning by doing.**
- Focusing on so-called **flash education** i.e., short, condensed learning experiences and **micro-credentialling**.

From the audience came **interesting insights** on:

- The current **diversity of experiences** in the training available across Europe (one country’s experiences in digital skills, for example, may be much more advanced and mature than another’s).
- The fact that members of the workforce “*cannot add yet another [university] degree*” to their **portfolio of skills**.
- Enabling the **experience and immediacy** of learning “*lightbulb moments*”.

In a nutshell

While most of the break-out’s focus was on immediate solutions, **longer-term and future-facing concerns** were also important. Overall, the four panellists expressed their interest in **future collaborations**.

What’s in it for you?

- Learn more from the experiences of **partnerships and initiatives** such as:
 - BeWell⁴
 - BRIGHTskills⁵
 - European Health Futures Forum⁶
 - SUSa project⁷
 - XiA project⁸
 - **A shared collaboration**⁹ between XiA and BeWell.

⁴ <https://bewell-project.eu/partnership/>

⁵ <https://www.bright-skills.eu>

⁶ <https://ehff.eu/what-we-do/>

⁷ <https://susacampus.eu>

⁸ <https://xia-project.iscte-iul.pt/news/>

⁹ <https://xia-project.iscte-iul.pt/xia-and-bewell-exchange-on-skills-strategies-for-europes-health-workforce/>